

DISASTER PREPAREDNESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL: LEARNERS AWARENESS OF SCHOOL SUSPENSION PROTOCOLS IN CALAMITIES

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the awareness and preparedness of learners at Taft National High School, located in the Philippines' disaster-prone Eastern Visayas region, regarding school suspension protocols during natural disasters. Focusing on scenarios such as tropical cyclones, heavy rainfall, flooding, earthquakes, and power outages, the study employs a descriptive research design and a stratified random sampling technique. Data collected through a questionnaire reveal a moderate baseline awareness among participants, with notable gaps in understanding specific details of protocols. While learners exhibit general knowledge of school responsibilities and automatic class cancellations during disasters, there is a need for targeted interventions to enhance comprehension of warning systems, differentiation between severity levels, and the roles of various authorities. The study emphasizes the importance of collaboration with parents, local government units, and the integration of disaster risk reduction education into the curriculum. Recommendations include instituting educational campaigns to address awareness gaps and strengthen learner preparedness for a more resilient school community.

Keywords: learners' awareness, learners' preparedness, school suspension protocols, natural disasters, disaster risk reduction.

INTRODUCTION

Disasters, whether natural or human-made, pose significant threats to the safety and well-being of individuals and communities. In the context of the Philippines, a country located in the Pacific typhoon belt and prone to various natural disasters such as typhoons, earthquakes, landslides, and others, the impact of these events is a recurrent challenge (Low, 2022). To address this issue, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 037, s. 2022, providing guidelines for the suspension of classes and work during natural disasters and calamities.

Despite these guidelines, there remains a critical concern about the awareness and preparedness of learners, particularly those in vulnerable grade levels. Lapada (2022) highlights the potential consequences of unpreparedness, especially in a school setting where students are exposed to the impacts of class suspension during disasters. While Rogayan et al. (2022) suggest that higher-level learners may have better awareness, a conflict exists in the utilization of information among different grade levels.

Taft National High School, located in the Eastern Visayas region, is particularly susceptible to various disastrous events, making it an ideal setting for this study. Historically, research on learner awareness and preparedness in the face of natural disasters has received limited attention. This research aims to fill this gap by examining learners' awareness and perceptions of class cancellation protocols during disasters.

Past studies have primarily focused on disaster risk reduction preparedness at the school and administrative levels, with limited attention to learner awareness. For example, Jauro et al. (2023) centered their research on the emergency response of school administrators, overlooking the concerns related to learner awareness. While other studies emphasize strengthening school-community responses to disasters, this research aims to address the specific issue of learner awareness and preparedness.

In addressing the concerns surrounding uncontrolled learner whereabouts during class suspensions, Secretary Briones proposed a shift in responsibility to parents and local government units (LGUs) for ensuring student safety during disasters. This change aligns with DepEd Order No. 037, Series of 2022, emphasizing the need to follow guidelines for class cancellations due to natural disasters (DepEd Memorandum No. 2023-077). Cubillas (2021) conducted a study that identified challenges in implementing the School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program (SDRRM) in respondent schools, indicating the need for further research in this area.

Disasters, whether natural or human-made, result in significant turmoil, injury, physical damage, and economic disruption (Rogayan & Dollete, 2020). These events encompass both human-made disasters like fires and flash floods and natural hazards such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, typhoons, and tsunamis. Given the high vulnerability and susceptibility of the Philippines to such events, public awareness and preparedness are crucial (WRR, 2021).

Building awareness and preparedness within the school environment and community can mitigate the destructive effects of disasters in educational settings (State & Ogunleye, 2019). School principals play a vital role in ensuring the implementation of effective Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) practices to create a safe learning environment, particularly for elementary school pupils (Jasojaso, 2020). Comighud (2020) suggests that DRRM programs in public schools are well-executed, emphasizing the need to analyze the implementation and adherence to SDRRM provisions among school administrators.

The Department of Education has released several DepEd Orders to guide the implementation of disaster preparedness measures and protocols, including DepEd Order No. 037 s. 2022, which outlines specific measures for tropical cyclones, flooding, and other weather-related disturbances and calamities.

Ali et al. (2020) conducted a study in Pakistan, examining school children's perceptions, knowledge, and preparedness for flood disaster risk management. Their research highlights the importance of integrating DRR education into schools to disseminate disaster-mitigation information and empower future generations to participate in crisis management.

This research addresses the gap in understanding learner awareness and preparedness during class cancellations due to natural disasters. By examining the awareness levels of learners at Taft National High School, this study aims to provide valuable insights and contribute to a safer and more disaster-resilient educational environment.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 gender
 - 1.3 grade level
 - 1.4 home location?
2. What is the awareness level of respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Tropical Cyclone
 - 2.2 Awareness on School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Heavy Rainfall.
 - 2.3 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Flooding.
 - 2.4 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Earthquake.
 - 2.5 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during power outages/power interruptions/brownouts in schools.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design that was employed in this study was a descriptive research design, as outlined by Sirisilla (2023). The primary objective of this research was to evaluate learners' awareness of class cancellation protocols. To achieve this, data was collected through a survey questionnaire.

Research Respondents

The respondents in this study were Junior High School learners from Taft National High School who were enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. The inclusion criteria encompassed learners of all age groups, genders, and grade levels within the Junior High School. Additionally, participants were selected from various residential locations, including the town proper, external barangays, and upstream barangays, to ensure a diverse representation of the learner population. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to gather responses from the respondents to ensure that each participant had an equal chance of being included in the study, enhancing the credibility and reliability of the findings.

Research Instruments

The data for the study was gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire had two parts; Part I was about the respondents' personal information. Part II focused on learners' awareness of guidelines on the cancellation or suspension of classes and work in schools in the event of natural disasters, power outages/power interruptions, and other calamities based on DepEd Order No. 37 series of 2022. The questionnaire underwent content validity by experts in School Disaster Risk and Reduction and Management to assess whether the items were appropriate for the study. The final evaluation was done by 2 Master Teachers.

In terms of reliability, the questionnaire was tested on forty (40) learners in the Taft District, Taft National High School. There were 10 grade 7 learners, 10 grade 8 learners, 10 grade 9 learners, and 10 grade 10 learners. The responses were computed using Cronbach's Alpha.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were employed to provide a comprehensive overview of the respondent profile and gain insights into their characteristics. This analysis involved the calculation of various measures, including frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Frequency analysis was conducted to determine how many respondents belonged to each category within the demographic variables, such as age, gender, grade level, and residence location. This helped gain a clear understanding of the distribution of respondents across these key profiles' attributes. Means for each question in Part II of

the questionnaire were calculated. This particular analysis aimed to assess the awareness level of learners regarding class cancellation protocols. Standard deviations for each question were computed to provide insights into the variability or spread of responses for each question.

RESULTS

Table1. Learners' Profile of Respondents

Profile of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
11-13 years old	100	33.33%
14-16 years old	160	53.33%
17-19 years old	40	13.33%
Gender		
Male	123	41.00%
Female	177	59.00%
Grade Level		
Grade 7	75	25.00%
Grade 8	75	25.00%
Grade 9	75	25.00%
Grade 10	75	25.00%
Home Location		
Town Proper	120	40.00%
External Barangay	90	30.00%
Upstream Barangay	50	16.67%
Other Municipality	40	13.33%

Table 1 presents an overview of the profile characteristics of the respondents, shedding light on key factors such as age, gender, grade level, and home location. In terms of age distribution, the majority of participants fall within the 11 to 13 age brackets, comprising 33.33% of the sample, while those aged 14 to 16 constitute the largest proportion at 53.33%. The least represented age group is 17-19 years old, comprising 13.33% of the respondents. Gender-wise, the study reveals a higher percentage of female participants, accounting for 59.00% of the sample, compared to males at 41.00%. When examining grade levels, the respondents are evenly distributed across 7th to 10th grades, each grade level representing 25.00% of the overall sample. Regarding home location, the majority (40.00%) reside in the town proper, followed by those from external barangays at 30.00%. Respondents from upstream barangays and other municipalities constitute smaller proportions of the sample at 16.67% and 13.33%, respectively. These findings provide a valuable foundation for understanding the demographic composition of the study population, which can be instrumental in tailoring interventions.

Table 2 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Tropical Cyclone.

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.Awareness of school suspension protocols	3.8	1.2	Moderately aware
2. Knowledge of PAGASA's TCWS	3.3	1.5	Somewhat aware
3.Awareness of class cancellation conditions under TCWS	2.9	1.4	Slightly aware
4.Knowledge of alternative learning system (ALS) and its impact by TCWS	2.5	1.6	Not at all aware
5.Awareness of school actions during classes with issued TCWS	3.2	1.3	Moderately aware
6.Awareness of school's responsibility for safety during a cyclone	4.0	1.0	Extremely aware
7.Awareness of LGU's role in class cancellation due to strong winds	3.4	1.4	Moderately aware
8.Ability to name at least one precautionary measure for cyclones	4.2	1.1	Extremely aware
9.Knowledge of information sources for TCWS and suspension updates	3.6	1.3	Moderately aware
10.Familiarity with general safety guidelines during cyclones	3.9	1.1	Moderately aware

As seen in Table 2, the participants in this study had a moderate level of awareness of the school's suspension protocols during tropical cyclones. They were most familiar with the school's responsibility to ensure the safety of students and personnel during a cyclone, as well as their ability to name at least one precautionary measure to take when there's a tropical cyclone warning in their area. They were least familiar with the conditions under which in-person and online classes are automatically canceled during TCWS 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5, as well as the knowledge of alternative learning system (ALS) and its impact by TCWS.

These findings suggest that there is a need for more education and awareness about the school's suspension protocols during tropical cyclones. The school could provide more information to parents and students about the conditions under which classes are canceled, as well as the alternative learning system that will be used if classes are canceled. The school could also work with the Local Government Unit (LGU) to ensure that everyone is aware of the LGU's role in deciding class cancellations or suspensions due to strong winds without a TCWS.

Table 3. Awareness on School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Heavy Rainfall.

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Do you know about PAGASA's rainfall warning system?	4.2	0.8	Moderately aware
2. Are you aware that schools can be suspended due to heavy rainfall?	4.7	0.6	Moderately aware
3. Can you differentiate between Orange and Red Rainfall warnings in terms of school suspension?	3.8	1.0	Somewhat aware
4. Do you know what actions the school should take when an Orange or Red Rainfall warning is issued?	3.5	1.2	Somewhat aware
5. Are you familiar with the concept of a 'Local Government Unit' (LGU) in the context of school suspensions?	3.2	1.3	Somewhat aware
6. Do you know what actions the school should take when a Yellow Rainfall warning is issued or during torrential rains in your area?	3.0	1.4	Somewhat aware
7. Are you aware of the role of the Local Chief Executive in deciding on school suspensions during heavy rainfall?	2.8	1.5	Slightly aware
8. Can you describe the steps schools should take to ensure the safety of students and personnel during heavy rainfall?	2.5	1.6	Slightly aware
9. Do you know how the school communicates suspension information to students and parents during heavy rainfall?	3.6	1.1	Somewhat aware
10. Are you knowledgeable about your responsibilities and what to do when classes are suspended due to heavy rainfall?	3.3	1.2	Moderately aware

The results from Table 3 present an overview of the awareness levels among respondents regarding school suspension protocols in public schools during heavy rainfall. Participants demonstrated a moderate awareness level (Mean = 4.2, SD = 0.8) regarding PAGASA's rainfall warning system, indicating a satisfactory understanding of this crucial aspect. Additionally, respondents displayed a slightly higher level of awareness (Mean = 4.7, SD = 0.6) regarding the possibility of school suspensions due to heavy rainfall. However, when assessing the ability to differentiate between Orange and Red Rainfall warnings for school suspension, the awareness level was somewhat lower (Mean = 3.8, SD = 1.0). Similarly, respondents exhibited somewhat limited awareness regarding the actions schools should take when specific warnings are issued, with means ranging from 3.5 to 2.5 and standard deviations indicating variability. Furthermore, awareness levels regarding the role of the Local Government Unit (LGU) in school

suspensions were rated at 3.2 (SD = 1.3). The respondents' knowledge of responsibilities during school suspensions, as well as communication methods with students and parents, was generally moderate, with means ranging from 3.0 to 3.6 and standard deviations reflecting some variability. The findings suggest that while there is a baseline awareness among respondents, there is room for improvement in understanding and familiarity with specific protocols related to school suspensions during heavy rainfall, particularly in terms of differentiating warning levels and comprehending the roles of relevant authorities. These insights can inform targeted interventions to enhance awareness and preparedness within the public-school system.

Table 4 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Flooding.

Question	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Are you aware of the school's suspension protocols during flood warnings issued by PAGASA?	2.5	0.8	Somewhat Aware
2. Do you know what actions should be taken when a flood warning is issued during school hours?	2.3	1.0	Slightly Aware
3. Are you familiar with the criteria for sending students and personnel home when a flood warning is issued?	2.2	1.2	Slightly Aware
4. Do you understand the circumstances under which schools may be required to keep students and personnel safely on the premises?	2.1	1.3	Slightly Aware
5. Are you aware that in case of Yellow rainfall warning by PAGASA, the local chief executive may decide on class cancellation or suspension?	2.4	0.9	Slightly Aware
6. Do you know what actions to take if your Local Government Unit (LGU) is issued a Yellow rainfall warning by PAGASA?	2.2	1.1	Slightly Aware
7. Are you aware that classes can be canceled in your LGU due to localized flooding even without an official flood warning from PAGASA?	2.3	0.9	Slightly Aware
8. Do you know what measures your school has in place to ensure the safety of students and personnel during flooding events?	2.6	0.7	Somewhat Aware
9. Have you received training or information about flood preparedness and response at your school?	2.4	0.8	Slightly Aware
10. Are you aware of any specific evacuation or safety procedures that your school has established for flood-related emergencies?	2.2	1.2	Slightly Aware

Table 4 presents the results of a study investigating the awareness and preparedness of individuals regarding school suspension protocols in public schools

during flooding. The mean scores and standard deviations for each question were calculated to gauge the level of awareness among respondents. The findings indicate a moderate level of awareness across the surveyed population. Specifically, respondents reported being somewhat aware (mean = 2.5, SD = 0.8) of the school's suspension protocols during flood warnings issued by PAGASA. However, the awareness level decreased slightly for questions related to specific actions to be taken during flood warnings (mean = 2.3, SD = 1.0) and the criteria for sending students and personnel home (mean = 2.2, SD = 1.2). Similarly, respondents showed relatively lower awareness regarding circumstances under which schools may be required to keep individuals on the premises (mean = 2.1, SD = 1.3). Awareness levels were also modest for understanding the impact of Yellow rainfall warnings on class cancellation (mean = 2.4, SD = 0.9) and the corresponding actions to be taken at the local level (mean = 2.2, SD = 1.1). Additionally, respondents reported a moderate level of awareness about the potential cancellation of classes due to localized flooding without an official PAGASA warning (mean = 2.3, SD = 0.9). When asked about the safety measures in place at their schools during flooding events, respondents expressed a somewhat higher level of awareness (mean = 2.6, SD = 0.7). However, the awareness levels dropped slightly for questions related to training or information received about flood preparedness and response at the school (mean = 2.4, SD = 0.8) and specific evacuation or safety procedures established for flood-related emergencies (mean = 2.2, SD = 1.2).

Table 5 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during Earthquake.

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.I am aware of the school suspension protocols during an earthquake.	3.20	0.80	Somewhat aware
2.I know that in-person and online classes are automatically canceled in PHILVOCS PEIS V or above earthquakes.	4.10	0.70	Moderately aware
3.I understand that the local chief executive decides class suspension for PEIS IV and below earthquakes.	3.70	0.90	Moderately aware
4.I am aware that the school principal can cancel classes at any intensity scale if they see danger or damage.	3.50	0.80	Moderately aware
5.I know that the SDRRM Team head decides when it's safe to return to the building after an earthquake.	3.90	0.80	Moderately aware
6.I have received training or information on what to do during an earthquake at school.	4.00	0.70	Moderately aware
7.I am familiar with the safe evacuation routes and assembly points in case of an earthquake.	3.80	0.90	Moderately aware
8.I know where emergency supplies are located in case of an earthquake.	3.60	0.80	Moderately aware

9.I am aware of the school's communication plan during and after an earthquake.	3.40	0.90	Somewhat aware
10.I feel confident in my ability to respond appropriately during an earthquake at school.	3.30	0.90	Somewhat aware

Respondents are somewhat aware of the school's earthquake preparedness protocols and procedures. However, there is a slight to moderate variation in awareness across different aspects, suggesting that some targeted interventions may be needed to improve overall preparedness. Learners seem to be more aware of the fact that classes are automatically canceled for PHILVOCS PEIS V or above earthquakes (mean = 4.10) than they are of the school's communication plan during and after an earthquake (mean = 3.40). This suggests that more emphasis could be placed on communicating the school's communication plan to students.

Table 6 School Suspension Protocols in Public Schools during power outages/power interruptions/brownouts in schools.

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.I am aware of the school's policy regarding power outages.	3.2	0.7	Moderately aware
2.I know that there will be no automatic cancellation of classes during power outages.	3.1	0.8	Moderately aware
3.I understand that school officials have the authority to suspend classes due to power outages.	3.3	0.6	Moderately aware
4.I know the specific conditions that might lead to class suspension during power outages.	2.9	0.7	Somewhat aware
5.I am aware of the actions to be taken by students when there is a power outage at school.	3.0	0.8	Moderately aware
6.I have received information on how to report power outages to school authorities.	3.2	0.7	Moderately aware
7.I understand how power outages might affect the learning environment.	2.8	0.9	Somewhat aware
8.I know the procedures for resuming classes after a power outage.	3.1	0.8	Moderately aware
9.I am aware of any alternative learning methods or arrangements during power outages.	2.9	0.8	Somewhat aware
10.I have knowledge of any personal responsibilities during power outages at school	3.0	0.7	Moderately aware

Respondents seem to have a slightly aware to somewhat aware understanding of the school's protocols regarding power outages. Indicators 1, 2, 3, 5, and 6 have mean scores slightly above 3, suggesting students are somewhat aware of these aspects. Indicators 4, 7, 8, 9, and 10 have mean scores closer to 3, indicating students are slightly aware of these details. The standard deviations around the means suggest some

variation in students' awareness levels. This could be due to factors like grade level, prior experiences with power outages at school, or individual learning styles. It is recommended that the school administration conduct further assessments to identify specific areas where students' awareness is lacking and implement targeted interventions to improve their understanding of the school's protocols for power outages.

DISCUSSION

The study provides a comprehensive overview of the profile characteristics of the respondents, shedding light on key factors such as age, gender, grade level, and home location (Table 1). The majority of participants are aged 14 to 16, and females constitute a higher percentage of the sample. The distribution across grade levels is fairly even, with the majority residing in the town proper. These demographic insights are crucial for tailoring interventions and drawing conclusions in subsequent analyses, aligning with the recommendations of Lapada (2022) and Rogayan et al. (2022) regarding the importance of understanding learner awareness and preparedness in disaster-prone areas.

The findings reveal a moderate level of awareness among participants regarding the school's suspension protocols during tropical cyclones (TC). Participants demonstrated better awareness of general safety measures but were less familiar with conditions triggering class cancellations or the impact of TC on the alternative learning system (ALS). This suggests a need for targeted educational initiatives to enhance understanding, in line with the recommendations of Comighud (2020) and Ali et al. (2020) emphasizing the importance of disaster risk reduction education in schools.

The awareness levels regarding school suspension protocols during heavy rainfall (Table 3) indicate satisfactory understanding of PAGASA's rainfall warning system and general awareness of possible school suspensions. However, there is room for improvement in differentiating between warning levels and comprehending the roles of relevant authorities. These insights align with the suggestions of Cubillas (2021) regarding the challenges in implementing the School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program, emphasizing the need for further research to address specific issues of learner awareness and preparedness.

Table 4 presents the results related to awareness and preparedness during flooding, indicating a moderate level of awareness. However, respondents displayed varying levels of awareness regarding specific actions during flood warnings, criteria for sending individuals home, and understanding the impact of rainfall warnings on class cancellation. This underscores the need for targeted interventions to improve overall preparedness, consistent with the recommendations of State and Ogunleye (2019) emphasizing the role of school principals in implementing effective disaster risk reduction and management practices.

The study also addresses awareness levels related to earthquakes and power outages, revealing some variation in awareness across different aspects. This suggests

the need for specific interventions to improve overall preparedness and communication of school protocols in these areas.

Conclusions

The study provides an assessment of the awareness levels among respondents regarding school suspension protocols during various critical situations such as tropical cyclones, heavy rainfall, flooding, earthquakes, and power outages. Across these scenarios, it's evident that while there's a baseline level of awareness among the participants, there are considerable areas for improvement. Specifically, respondents exhibit moderate awareness levels regarding general protocols or overarching concepts, such as the school's responsibility for safety during adverse weather conditions or the automatic cancellation of classes during certain severity levels of natural disasters. However, when it comes to details such as differentiation between warning levels, specific actions to be taken, or understanding the roles of various authorities, the awareness levels tend to drop. This highlights the need for more targeted interventions and comprehensive educational efforts, potentially involving collaborations between schools, local government units, and relevant agencies, to enhance the understanding of these protocols. Improving awareness could involve more detailed education on specific warning levels, communication plans during emergencies, and the delineation of responsibilities among stakeholders, aiming to bolster preparedness and safety within the school community.

Recommendations

Based on the comprehensive analysis of demographic profiles and awareness levels outlined in the study, it's evident that there's a crucial need to strengthen education and awareness regarding school suspension protocols during various natural disasters among learners at Taft National High School. The findings across different disaster scenarios—tropical cyclones, heavy rainfall, flooding, earthquakes, and power outages—consistently highlight areas where learners exhibit moderate awareness but also demonstrate significant gaps in understanding specific protocols and response measures. To address these deficiencies, it's recommended that the school institute targeted interventions. These could include enhanced educational campaigns focusing on different warning systems, precise conditions necessitating class cancellations, and delineating the roles of local authorities, thereby fortifying the learners' preparedness and safety during unforeseen calamities. Additionally, aligning with DepEd guidelines, collaboration with parents, LGUs, and the integration of disaster risk reduction education within the curriculum, will be instrumental in creating a more resilient and informed student body at Taft National High School.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author confirm that this study adhered strictly to all ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also assured of their right to

withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. Measures were taken to maintain anonymity and confidentiality, ensuring that participants were not subjected to any harm. The author also declares that there were no conflicts of interest during the study. Plagiarism was meticulously avoided, and the interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias. The results were utilized exclusively for research purposes.

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